

STRUCTURE AND CONTENT OF GENERAL PSYCHOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF HIGHLY SKILLED PARALYMPIC ATHLETES

Azizbek Khoshimovich Uzokov¹

Annagurtov Mo'min Akhmatovich²

^{1,2}State University of Physical Education and Sports of Uzbekistan
Uzbekistan, Chirchik city

E-mail: uzoqov93@internet.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7491018>

Abstract

With the emergence of paralympic sports and new sciences with their own characteristics, the issue of scientific justification of the structure and content of psychological preparation of paralympic athletes at different stages and periods of sports training, taking into account nosologies, is becoming urgent. The use of psychosportograms derived from Olympic sports research is only partially transferable to Paralympic disciplines and requires further development to identify appropriate tools and methods.

Keywords: sports psychology, periodization of sports training, Paralympic sports, high sports skills

Enter. Modern sports psychology is not only different fields of knowledge psychology, pedagogy, psychophysiology, theory and methodology of physical education, but also different psychological schools, including cognitive, behavioral, personality-oriented, gestalt, existential, clinical, etc., it is local and It is reflected in various research directions of foreign authors. In this regard, there are inconsistencies in the terms and definitions used in the description. The studied phenomena and processes in the psychological preparation of the athlete, as well as the use of diagnostic methods and effects. [1,11,21,31,41,51,61,71,8,97]

The approach we propose is based on the consideration of sports in the paradigm of professional activity that dominates the lifestyle of an athlete who performs daily work on the development of innate abilities, certain qualities, formation and improvement of necessary knowledge. Acquires life skills and strives to maximize their talents in high achievement. Psychological preparation, as well as physical, technical, tactical, sports training is carried out at each stage in the amount determined by federal standards. In this regard, both in the structure and content of psychological training, it is necessary to plan training that matches the age characteristics of athletes, training periods, as well as the volume of training and competitive loads. [8,18,28,38,48,58,68,78,88,92]

Currently, the concept of periodization is the basis for planning and managing a sports training program. includes directions. There are specific characteristics of training periodization (micro, meso, macrocycles) for various sports and disciplines. Thus, psychological training in sports should be carried out in accordance with the nature of periodicity characteristic of a particular type of sport. [2,12,22,32,42,52,62,72,82,96]

In modern sports and disciplines, each of them imposes certain requirements on mental processes and psychological qualities of the athlete. Among the many domestic and foreign works devoted to psychographic analysis of sports activities and the creation of psychosportograms, an integrated approach that covers various aspects of training and competitions is psychological-pedagogical analysis of sports activities. Based on the

psychological theory of AN Leontiev's activity, a scheme for the analysis of psychological factors in various sports was created, according to which psychosportograms developed can serve to justify the structure and content of psychological training in certain sports. With the emergence of paralympic sports and new sciences with their own characteristics, the issue of scientific justification of the structure and content of psychological preparation of paralympic athletes at different stages and periods of sports training, taking into account nosologies, is becoming urgent. The use of psychosportograms derived from Olympic sports research is only partially transferable to Paralympic disciplines and requires further development to identify appropriate tools and methods.

The purpose of the study is to reveal the characteristics of the structure and content of general psychological training in Paralympic sports at different stages and taking into account nosologies.

Research results and conclusions. Methodological foundations, modern approaches and concepts of effective planning, organization and implementation of general psychological training in Paralympic sports are defined. It was determined that it is necessary to take into account the international paralympic sports classification, which belongs to different sports categories, which determines the specificity of the organization and conduct of the psychological preparation of high-class paralympic athletes. The characteristics of the structure and content of the general psychological preparation of Paralympic athletes at the stages of sports specialization and high sports skills are revealed. [9,19,29,39,49,59,69,79,87,91]

The authors conclude that the development of general psychological training programs of high-class Paralympic athletes should be carried out in the paradigm of professional activity, based on the concept of periodization of sports training, based on the characteristics of a specific sport. taking into account the sports class, the level of existing functional injuries. It is desirable to use a model-targeted approach to the mental sphere of paralympians using psycho-pedagogical methods that take into account innate individual characteristics and the influence of physical activity, social relations and the environment

Today, Paralympic sports have absorbed many features of Olympism and turned from a means of adaptation and rehabilitation of the disabled into an independent Paralympic movement with a system of sports training from elementary to high performance, regulated by federal standards and various levels of legislation. Planning and implementation of psychological preparation for Paralympic sports is one of the most relevant areas of research both in our country and abroad, but at the current stage it is little studied. [3,13,23,33,43,53,63,73,83,95]

The main distinguishing feature of Paralympic sports is the classification of sports, which provides equal opportunities for competition for people with various functional disabilities and defines the specific features of the competition rules, which differ from Olympic disciplines. The various functional disorders regulated by sport classification make significant changes in the planning and implementation of the general psychological preparation of Paralympic athletes. In this regard, more extensive scientific research is required to learn to take into account nosological features in the process of psychological preparation using hardware methods (in addition to personality features, the presence of psychological injuries caused by disability). In addition, attention should be paid to the specific functional lesion, which is often used by healthy athletes against the use of generally accepted methods in

sports, such as deep lung ventilation or breathing techniques with light and sound stimulation. is a guideline. [5,15,25,35,45,55,65,75,85,94]

The composition of psychological training includes general and special psychological training, each of which is carried out in a certain period of sports training and solves its tasks accordingly. Since the formation and improvement of the athlete's psychological readiness takes place precisely in the system of sports training, under the influence of loads, characteristics of the sport, and the relationship between the participants of the training process, it is appropriate to perform general exercises.

The structure and content of general psychological preparation of Paralympic athletes. With the increase in the number of competitions and the accumulation of competition experience at the stage of high sports skills, the main attention in general psychological preparation is transferred to the analysis of competition activities. As part of individual consultations, it is recommended to analyze successful and unsuccessful indicators at the beginning of the transition period of sports training, when the volume and intensity of physical activity has significantly decreased. Yu. It is advisable to follow L. Khanin's concept of individual zones of optimal performance (IZOF). This highest achievement has been confirmed by many foreign studies in various sports. It allows the athlete to fully immerse himself in past competitions, to realize his feelings and emotional experiences at the start, to understand the cause-and-effect relationship of his actions, the decisions made in the conditions of intense competition and, as a result, provides full understanding. , identifying and defining an individual zone of optimal performance as a target state of "flow"; learn to model upcoming situations and make reasonable predictions about your success. [7,17,27,37,47,57,67,87,93]

In our study of Paralympic athletes' mental state self-regulation in archery and athletics with PDA during pre-competition and transition training during a two-year sport training cycle, Spinal Cord Injury , significant features of galvanic skin responses (GSR) indicators in wheelchair athletes with multiple functional injuries of the trunk and limbs: low background level of GSR ($p \leq 0.05$, $p \leq 0, 01$) and small ranges of relaxation and activation ($p \leq 0.05$). It was found that during the transition period of sports training, the background level of GSR differed significantly between the groups of athletes with amputations due to dysmelia and injuries and athletes with impairments caused by cerebral palsy. The obtained results confirm the need to individualize the training process of paralympians.

At the stage of specialization in sports, it is appropriate to pay attention to the improvement of self-regulation skills and the development of special psychological qualities formed in the previous stages of sports training. This approach is aimed at developing the discipline of athletes and involving them more consciously in the training process, as it includes extensive independent work under periodic supervision by a specialist. For its implementation, the Russian version of the Swedish model of mental training was developed, which proves its effectiveness in training athletes at the stage of sports specialization.

Summary. Thus, the development of general psychological training programs of high-class Paralympic athletes should be carried out in the paradigm of professional activity based on the concept of periodization of sports training, taking into account the characteristics of a particular type of sport. belonging to the sports class, the level of existing functional disorders. Taking into account the inherent individual characteristics of physical activity, social relations and the influence of the environment on the mental sphere of Paralympic athletes, it is recommended to use a model-targeted approach using psychological-pedagogical methods.

References:

1. БОЛАЛАР ВА ЎСМИРЛАР СПОРТ МАКТАБЛАРИДА БОШЛАНҒИЧ ТАЙЁРЛОВ ГУРУҲИДА ШУҒУЛЛАНУВЧИ ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАР МАШҒУЛОТЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ Ғофуров Ш.Х. Фан-Спортга. 2020. № 5. С. 38-40.
2. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAГИ BOLALARNI YENGIL АТЛЕТИКА MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022)
3. M. X.Mirjamolov, R. F.Odilov, N. Y.Valiyeva, D. B.Baxtiyorov KO'RISH QOBILYATIDA NUQSONI BO'LGAN TALABALARDA HARAKAT KOORDINATSIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH USLUBIYATI // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №12. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ko-rish-qobilyatida-nuqsoni-bo-lgan-talabalarda-harakat-koordinatsiyasini-rivojlantirish-uslubiyati> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022)
4. M. X. Миржамолов, Р. Ф. Одилов, Н. Ю. Валиева, Д. Б. Бахтиёров МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ КООРДИНАЦИИ ДВИЖЕНИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ С НАРУШЕНИЯМИ ЗРЕНИЯ // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/metodika-razvitiya-koordinatsii-dvizheniy-u-studentov-s-narusheniyami-zreniya> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022).
5. Kh M. M., Svetlichnaya N. K. Abdiev Sh. A., Davlatova LT, Sobirova LB Improving Pedagogical Mechanisms to Increase Special Physical Preparation of Students with Disabilities in Uzbekistan //Psychology and education. – 2021. – Т. 58. – №. 2. – С. 1379-1389
6. Lola Tilapovna Davlatova JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORTDA SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH TEXNOLOGIYALARINING DOLZARBLIGI VA AHAMIYATI // Scientific progress. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/jismoniy-tarbiya-va-sportda-sog-lomlashtirish-texnologiyalarining-dolzarbligi-va-ahamiyati> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022)
7. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov MALAKALI SPINTERCHILARNING SPORT MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/malakali-sprinterchilarning-sport-mashg-ulotlarini-rivojlantirishning-usullari> (дата обращения: 28.12.2022).
8. Шерали Хошимович Ғофуров, Баҳодир Хошимович Ғофуров ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА 5Х5 ФУТБОЛ СПОРТ ТУРИНИ ОММАЛАШТИРИШ ОРҚАЛИ КЎРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИДА НУҚСОНИ БОР ШАХСЛАР ҲАРАКАТ ФАОЛЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zbekistonda-5x5-futbol-sport-turini-ommalashtirish-or-ali-k-rish-obiliyatida-nu-soni-bor-shahslar-arakat-faolligini-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022)
9. Sherali Xoshimovich G'Ofurov, Baxodir Xoshimovich G'Ofurov NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA POG'ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIYASI // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/nogironlar-aravachasidan-foydalanadigan-umurtqa-pog-onasi-shikastlangan-yoshlarning-adaptiv-jismoniy-tarbiyasi> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022).
10. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O. et al. Scientific progress. 2022. № 1 //URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 04.02. 2022).

11. Юнусов, С. А. "Физическое воспитание школьников в инклюзивном образовании" SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS." Scientific Journal ISSN (2021): 2181-1601
12. Charos Alisher Qizi Berdiyeva JISMONIY IMKONIYATI CHEKLANGAN TALABA QIZLARDA EGILUVCHANLIK VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISH USULIYATI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/jismoniy-imkoniyati-cheklangan-talaba-qizlarda-egiluvchanlik-va-uni-rivojlantirish-usuliyati> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022).
Рухиддин 2, [13.12.2022 11:28]
13. Ч. А. Бердиева ЖИСМОНИЙ ИМКОНИЯТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН ТАЛАБАЛАР ОРГАНИЗМИНИНГ ФУНКЦИОНАЛ ҲОЛАТИНИ БАҲОЛАШ УСУЛИ // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №Special Issue 1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zhismoniy-imkoniyati-cheklangan-talabalar-organizmining-funksional-olatini-ba-olash-usuli> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022)
14. Абдиев Ш.А. ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ЮҚОРИ МАЛАКАЛИ ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАРНИ МУСОБАҚА ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ РЕЖАЛАШТИРИШ // Fan-Sportga. 2020. №7. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparati-shikastlangan-yu-ori-malakali-engil-atletikachilarni-musoba-a-yuklamalarini-rezhalashtirish> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022).
15. Абдиев Ш.А. ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ЮҚОРИ МАЛАКАЛИ УЛОҚТИРУВЧИЛАРНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ МЕЪЁРЛАШ // Fan-Sportga. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparati-shikastlangan-yu-ori-malakali-ulo-tiruvchilarni-mash-ulot-yuklamalarini-meyorlash> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022)
16. Lola Tilopovna Davlatova ADAPTIV SPORT O'YINLARINI (VOLEYBOL) O'QITISH METODIKASIDA HARAKAT USLUBLARI VA QOIDALARI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/adaptiv-sport-o-yinlarini-volleybol-o-qitish-metodikasida-harakat-uslublari-va-qoidalari> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022).
17. Миржамолов М.Х. ПАРА-СПОРТЧИЛАРНИНГ КИНЕМАТИК ҲАРАКАТ ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ // Fan-Sportga. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/para-sportchilarning-kinematik-arakat-imkoniyatlari-ta-lili> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022)
18. Бобомуродов, Н. Ш. "Структуры физической подготовленности курашистов" Вестник" науки и образования научно-методической журнал № 4 (82)." Часть 2.2020 (2020): 41-44
19. ЖИСМОНИЙ Л., НАЗАРИЙ Т., РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ С. Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. № Special Issue 1 //URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bolalar-tserebral-falazhida-zhismoniy-tayyorgarlikni-mash-ulot-zharayonida-va-ilmiy-nazariy-so-ada-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 12.01. 2022).
20. BOLALAR V. A. O'smirlar SPOR MAKTABLARIDA SPORCHILAR TAYYORLANISHINI TAKILISH BOSHLANGAN MASHG'ULOT GURUHI GofurovSh //X. Fan-Sportga. – 2020. – №. 5. – С. 38-40.
21. Еофуров Ш. NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA POG'ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIIYASI //МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКАЯ ОНЛАЙН КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ. – 2021. – Т. 4. – С. 24.

22. Sherali

Hoshimovich, G. O., Dilshod Baxtiyor, O. G., & Li Baxtiyorov, U. A. S. (2022). Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni yengil atletika mashqlari orqali mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etish. Scientific progress, (1).

23. Odilov R.F., Valiyeva N.Y.Q. Sensor tizimida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar mashg'ulotlarini kompleks nazorat qilish //Scientific progress. – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 8. – С. 670-674.

24. Миржамолов М. Х., Одилов Р. Ф., Зокиров Д. Р. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ СТУДЕНТОВ С ОГРАНИЧЕННЫМИ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЯМИ ЗДОРОВЬЯ //Актуальные проблемы физической культуры и спорта. – 2020. – С. 20-23.

25. Миржамолов М. Х. ЭШИТИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИ РИВОЖЛАНМАГАН ЎҚУВЧИЛАРДА ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАРБИЯ МАШҒУЛОТЛАРИНИ ЎТҚАЗИШ УСЛУБИЯТИ //Scientific progress. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 214-221.

26. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov MALAKALI SPINTERCHILARNING SPORT MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/malakali-sprinterchilarning-sport-mashg-ulotlarini-rivojlantirishning-usullari> (дата обращения: 13.12.2022).

27. Еофуров Ш. Jismoniy tarbiya vositalari orqali sportchilarni o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish qobiliyatlarini shakllantirish. – 2020.

28. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDA GI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 13.12.2022).

29. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O. MALAKALI SPINTERCHILARNING SPORT MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – №. 4.

30. Л. Б. Собирова Эффективность использования специальных упражнений в профилактике нарушений роста у младших школьников // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №5.

31. Sherali Hoshimovich G. Ofurov Qisqa masofaga yuguruvchi sportchilarni mashg'ulotlarini rivojlantirishning usullari //Scientific progress. – 2021. – №. 8.

32. ЖИСМОНИЙ Л., НАЗАРИЙ Т., РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ С. Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. № Special Issue 1 //URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bolalart-serebral-falazhida-zhismoniy-tayyorgarlikni-mash-ulot-zharayonida-va-ilmiy-nazariy-so-ada-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 12.01. 2022).

33. BOLALAR V. A. O'smirlar SPOR МАКТАБЛАРИДА SPORCHILAR TAYYORLANISHINI TAKILISH BOSHLANGAN MASHG'ULOT GURUHI GofurovSh //X. Fan-Sportga. – 2020. – №. 5. – С. 38-40.

34. Еофуров Ш. NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA POG'ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIYASI //МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКАЯ ОНЛАЙН КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ. – 2021. – Т. 4. – С. 24.

35.

ЕОФУРОВ Ш. МАКТАБЛАРИДА БОШЛАНЕИЧ ТАЙЁРЛОВ ГУРУ^ ИДА ШУЕУЛЛАНУВЧИ ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАР МАШЕУЛОТЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ. – 2020.

36. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O. MALAKALI SPRINTERCILARNING SPORT MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – №. 4.

37. Мехриддин Хайриддинович Миржамолов КҰРИШ ИМКОНИАТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН ШАХСЛАРДА СПОРТ ТЕХНИКАСИГА ҰРГАТИШНИНГ ҰЗИГА ХОС ЖИҲАТЛАРИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-rish-imkoniyati-cheklangan-shahslarda-sport-tehnikasiga-rgatishning-ziga-hos-zhi-atlari> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

38. Lola Tilopovna Davlatova ADAPTIV SPORT O'YINLARINI (VOLEYBOL) O'QITISH METODIKASIDA HARAKAT USLUBLARI VA QOIDALARI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/adaptiv-sport-o-yinlarini-volleybol-o-qitish-metodikasida-harakat-uslublari-va-qoidalari> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

39. Sherali Hoshimovich G. Ofurov Qisqa masofaga yuguruvchi sportchilarni mashg'ulotlarini rivojlantirishning usullari //Scientific progress. – 2021. – №. 8.

40. Л. Т. Давлатова БОЛАЛАР ЦЕРЕБРАЛ ФАЛАЖИДА ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИКНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЖАРАЁНИДА ВА ИЛМИЙ НАЗАРИЙ СОҲАДА РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №Special Issue 1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bolalar-tserebral-falazhida-zhismoniy-tayyorgarlikni-mash-ulot-zharayonida-va-ilmiy-nazariy-so-ada-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

41. Юнусов С. А. Особенности периодизации тренировочного процесса атлетов высококвалифицированных парапауэрлифтёров. – 2021.

42. Sherali Hoshimovich G., MASHG O. Q. M. Y. S., USULLARI U. R. Scientific progress. 2021. № 8 //URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/qisqa-masofaga-yuguruvchi-sportchilarni-mashg-ulotlarini-rivojlantirishning-usullari> (дата обращения: 12.01. 2022).

43. Гофуров Ш. Х. Баходир Хошимович Гофуров ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА 5X5 ФУТБОЛ СПОРТ ТУРИНИ ОММАЛАШТИРИШ ОРҚАЛИ КҰРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИДА НУҚСОНИ БОР ШАХСЛАР ҲАРАКАТ ФАОЛЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ //Scientific progress. – 2022. – Т. 6.

44. Gofurov S. X. et al. A STRATIFIED APPROACH IN IMPROVING THE PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF GIRLS WITH DISABILITIES //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 179-189.

45. Lola Tilapovna Davlatova JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORTDA SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH TECHNOLOGIYALARINING DOLZARBLIGI VA AHAMIYATI // Scientific progress. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/jismoniy-tarbiya-va-sportda-sog-lomlashtirish-technologiyalarining-dolzarbligi-va-ahamiyati> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

46. Л. Б.Собирова ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫХ УПРАЖНЕНИЙ В ПРОФИЛАКТИКЕ НАРУШЕНИЙ РОСТА У МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №5. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/effektivnost-ispolzovaniya-spetsialnyh-uprazhneniy-v-profilaktike-narusheniy-rosta-u-mladshih-shkolnikov> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

47. Kh M. M., Svetlichnaya N. K. Abdiev Sh. A., Davlatova LT, Sobirova LB Improving Pedagogical Mechanisms to Increase Special Physical Preparation of Students with Disabilities in Uzbekistan //Psychology and education. – 2021. – Т. 58. – №. 2. – С. 1379-1389.
48. Nurullayevna B. S., Sobirova L. МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA YASSI OYOQLIKNI JISMONIY MASHG'ULOTLARDA GIMNASTIKA VOSITALARI ORQALI OLDINI OLIISH //ТА'ЛИМ ВА RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 65-69.
49. Лайло Бахромовна Собирова ГОЛБОЛ-КЎРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИ БУЗИЛГАН БОЛАЛАРНИНГ КОРДИНАЦИОН ҚОБИЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ВОСИТАЛАРИ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/golbol-k-rish-obiliyati-buzilgan-bolalarning-kordinatsion-obiliyatini-rivozhlantirish-vositalari-samaradorligi> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
50. Еофуров Ш. Jismoniy tarbiya vositalari orqali sportchilarni o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish qobiliyatlarini shakllantirish. – 2020.
51. Sobirova L. B. THE USE PHYSICAL EDUCATION ARRANGEMENT TO PREVENT DISORDERS IN 7-10 GRADE PUPILS //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2020. – №. 3. – С. 411-415.
52. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O. et al. Scientific progress. 2022. № 1 //URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 04.02.2022).
53. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
54. М. Х. Миржамолов, Р. Ф. Одилов, Н. Ю. Валиева, Д. Б. Бахтиёров МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ КООРДИНАЦИИ ДВИЖЕНИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ С НАРУШЕНИЯМИ ЗРЕНИЯ // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/metodika-razvitiya-koordinatsii-dvizheniy-u-studentov-s-narusheniyami-zreniya> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
55. herali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
56. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O., Dilshod Baxtiyor O. G., Li Baxtiyorov U. A. S. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni yengil atletika mashqlari orqali mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etish //Scientific progress. – 2022. – №. 1.
57. Dilshod Baxtiyorovich Baxtiyorov AMPUNTANT FUTBOLCHILARNI JISMONIY TARBIYA VOSITALARI VA USLUBIYATI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ampuntant-futbolchilarni-jismoniy-tarbiya-vositalari-va-uslubiyati> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
58. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL:

- <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 28.12.2022).
59. Hoshimovich G. S., Duszhanov B. M., Abdumavlanovich T. U. IMPROVEMENT OF THE TRAINING PROCESS OF FLIGHT AND ATHLETS IN THE INITIAL TRAINING GROUP OF YOUTH // ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 163-176.
60. Абдиев Ш.А. ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ЮҚОРИ МАЛАКАЛИ УЛОҚТИРУВЧИЛАРНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ МЕЪЁРЛАШ // Fan-Sportga. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparati-shikastlangan-yu-ori-malakali-ulo-tiruvchilarni-mash-ulot-yuklamalarini-meyorlash> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022).
61. Шерзод Абдурахмонович Абдиев ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИДА НУҚСОНИ БЎЛГАН ЮҚОРИ МАЛАКАЛИ УЛОҚТИРУВЧИЛАРНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ ОПТИМАЛЛАШТИРИШ // Scientific progress. 2022. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparatida-nu-soni-b-lgan-yu-ori-malakali-ulo-tiruvchilarni-mash-ulot-yuklamalarini-optimallashtirish> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022).
62. ЕОФУРОВ Ш. МАКТАБЛАРИДА БОШЛАНЕИЧ ТАЙЁРЛОВ ГУРУ^ ИДА ШУЕУЛЛАНУВЧИ ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАР МАШЕУЛОТЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ. – 2020.
63. Абдиев Ш.А. Енгил атлетикани ўқитиш методикаси (Адаптив жисмоний тарбия ва спорт) // Ўқув қўлланма- Чирчиқ, Т.; 2020. - 200 б.
64. Миржамолов.М.Х., Абдиев Ш.А. Improving Pedagogical Mechanisms to Increase Special Physical Peregparation of Students with Disabilities in Uzbekistan.(2021) 58 (2) ISSN:00333077. 317 - 323 Pg.
65. Serali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov QISQA MASOFAGA YUGURUVCHI SPORTCHILARNI MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI // Scientific progress. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/qisqa-masofaga-yuguruvchi-sportchilarni-mashg-ulotlarini-rivojlantirishning-usullari> (дата обращения: 28.12.2022).
66. Миржамолов М. Х., Одилов Р. Ф., Валиева Н. Ю. ДБ Бахтиёров МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ КООРДИНАЦИИ ДВИЖЕНИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ С НАРУШЕНИЯМИ ЗРЕНИЯ //Scientific progress. – 2022. – №. 1.
67. Миржамолов М.Х. РИО-ДЕ ЖАНЕЙРО ШАҲРИДА БЎЛИБ ЎТГАН XV ВА ТОКИОДА БЎЛИБ ЎТГАН XVI ПАРАЛИМПИА УЙИНЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ // Fan-Sportga. 2021. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rio-de-zhaneyro-sha-rida-b-lib-tgan-xv-va-tokioda-b-lib-tgan-xvi-paralimpiya-yinlari-ta-lili> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
68. Миржамолов М. Х. Жисмоний имконияти чекланга укувчи-ларнинг спорт маршрутларига мослашиши //У^ ув услубий мажмуа, Тошкент. – 2014.
69. М. Х. Миржамолов, Р. Ф. Одилов, Н. Ю. Валиева, Д. Б. Бахтиёров МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ КООРДИНАЦИИ ДВИЖЕНИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ С НАРУШЕНИЯМИ ЗРЕНИЯ // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/metodika-razvitiya-koordinatsii-dvizheniy-u-studentov-s-narusheniyami-zreniya> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
70. Salomov R. S., Mirjamolov M. X. Adaptation of students with disabilities to sports is a teaching aid. – 2015.

71.

Мехриддин Хайриддинович Миржамолов КЎРИШ ИМКОНЯТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН ШАХСЛАРДА СПОРТ ТЕХНИКАСИГА ЎРГАТИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ЖИХАТЛАРИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-rish-imkoniyati-cheklangan-shahslarda-sport-tehnikasiga-rgatishning-ziga-hos-zhi-atlari> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

72. Миржамолов М.Х. ПАРА-СПОРТЧИЛАРНИНГ КИНЕМАТИК ҲАРАКАТ ИМКОНЯТЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ // Fan-Sportga. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/para-sportchilarning-kinematik-arakat-imkoniyatlari-tahlili> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

73. Gofurov S. X. et al. A STRATIFIED APPROACH IN IMPROVING THE PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF GIRLS WITH DISABILITIES //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 179-189.

74. Миржамолов М.Х. ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ПАРАЛИМПИА ҲАРАКАТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ВА ЗАХИРА СПОРТЧИЛАРНИ ТАЙЁРЛАШДА ИЛМИЙ ЁНДАШУВ // Fan-Sportga. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zbekistonda-paralimpiya-arakatini-rivozhlantirish-va-zahira-sportchilarni-tayyorlashda-ilmii-yondashuv> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

75. М. Х. Миржамолов ТАЯНЧ – ҲАРАКАТ АЪЗОЛАРИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ЎҚУВЧИЛАРДА МУСКУЛ ФАОЛИЯТИНИНГ БУЗИЛИШ ТАРТИБИ УЧУН ФУНКЦИОНАЛ ТИЗИМ ДИНАМИКАСИ // Scientific progress. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-azolari-shikastlangan-uvchilarda-muskul-faoliyatining-buzilish-tartibi-uchun-funksional-tizim-dinamikasi> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

76. Hoshimovich G. S., Duzhanov B. M., Abdumavlanovich T. U. IMPROVEMENT OF THE TRAINING PROCESS OF FLIGHT AND ATHLETS IN THE INITIAL TRAINING GROUP OF YOUTH //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 163-176.

77. Миржамолов М. Х. ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ, УЧАЩИХСЯ С ОГРАНИЧЕННЫМИ ФИЗИЧЕСКИМИ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЯМИ //Актуальные проблемы физической культуры и спорта. – 2019. – С. 50-55.

78. Миржамолов М. Х. Болалар мия фалажида тонус рефлексларининг таъсирини фитбол1 гимнастикаси ёрдамида ривожлантириш услубияти // Современное образование (Узбекистан). 2017. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bolalar-miya-falazhida-tonus-reflekslarining-tasirini-fitbol1-gimnastikasi-yordamida-rivozhlantirish-uslubiyati> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

79. Mirjamolov M. H. Evaluating Results of Functional Opportunities and Organism Systems Relationship of Students with Limited Physical Opportunity //www. auris-verlag. de. – 2017. – Т. 4. – С. 5.

80. Hayriddinovich M. M. THE RESULT OF THE MARKS OF MUTUAL DEPENDENCE BODY SYSTEM OF THE STUDENT'S WHOSE PHISICAL POSSIBILITY ARE LIMITED AND FUNCTIONAL CAPACITY //ББК 75.03 А 38. – С. 142.

81. Мехриддин Хайриддинович Миржамолов КЎРИШ ИМКОНЯТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН ШАХСЛАРДА СПОРТ ТЕХНИКАСИГА ЎРГАТИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ЖИХАТЛАРИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-rish-imkoniyati>

cheklangan-shahslarda-sport-tehnikasiga-rgatishning-ziga-hos-zhi-atlari (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

82. Sherali Xoshimovich G'Ofurov, Bahodir Xoshimovich G'Ofurov NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA POG'ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIYASI // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/nogironlar-aravachasidan-foydalanadigan-umurtqa-pog-onasi-shikastlangan-yoshlarning-adaptiv-jismoniy-tarbiyasi> (дата обращения: 28.12.2022).

83. Шерали Хошимович Гофуров, Баходир Хошимович Гофуров ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА 5X5 ФУТБОЛ СПОРТ ТУРИНИ ОММАЛАШТИРИШ ОРҚАЛИ КЎРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИДА НУҚСОНИ БОР ШАХСЛАР ҲАРАКАТ ФАОЛЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zbekistonda-5x5-futbol-sport-turini-ommalashtirish-or-ali-k-rish-obiliyatida-nu-soni-bor-shahslar-arakat-faolligini-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 28.12.2022).